

Deliverable No. 1.2

Project acronym:

FarFish

Project title:

Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

Grant agreement No: **727891**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme

Start date of project: **1st June 2017**

Duration: **48 months**

Due date of deliverable:	31/07/2019
Submission date:	20/08/2019
File Name:	FarFish_D1.2 Stakeholder Hub implementation
Revision number:	01
Document status:	Final ¹
Dissemination Level:	PU ²

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¹ Document will be a draft until it was approved by the coordinator

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Deliverable D1.2

Intermediate report on the Stakeholder Hub implementation: lessons learnt and improvement areas for the second spiral interaction

20/08/2019

Executive Summary

More than 20% of the European fishing fleets catches are taken from non-European waters. Access to these waters is often based on agreements with coastal states that allow the EU fleet to fish from surplus stocks in return for financial support. These agreements have been subjected to criticism, as these fisheries are sometimes poorly regulated and management decisions are often based on limited knowledge, compliance, and enforcement capabilities. It is also too often the case that trust between stakeholders is lacking. The aim of the FarFish project is to overcome these hurdles. The FarFish project is designed around six case study areas in which the European fleet is actively engaged in fishing activities, including Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and Seychelles, as well as the international high-seas areas in the southeast and southwest Atlantic.

FarFish aims to provide knowledge, tools and methods to support responsible, sustainable and profitable EU fisheries outside European waters. To achieve this, one of the implementation tools is the Stakeholder Hub, a multi-level and multi-stakeholder network integrated by scientists, policymakers, resource users, NGOs and other stakeholders aimed to improve fisheries management competences throughout their participation. The Stakeholder Hub is a responsive and flexible platform that adopts the form of a regional working group for the six case studies involved into the project, but adopting the form of a high-level European platform, or even an international forum for cross-cutting issues.

The design and implementation of the Stakeholder Hub, which combines physical events and e-communication, to match-up the project to the different stakeholder agendas, is requiring a certain stakeholder analysis to respond on who, what and when stakeholders should be part of the Hub.

Over the last decades, different approaches for stakeholders' analysis have been widely discussed in the stakeholder management literature. Stakeholder analysis is considered as a relevant tool to develop innovative management approaches for fisheries management. In fact, decision-makers have been recognizing for a long time the need to understand who is being affected by the actions, choices and decisions, and who has the power to influence their aims.

The Stakeholder Hub is a vital component of the FarFish project, as stakeholder analysis must be inserted from the interaction and the creation of governance networks to obtain insights into how these networks are delivering outcomes within the project. Taking into account the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) approach a framework for stakeholder analysis was selected, combining different theories. Therefore, the stakeholder analysis included in this report, is obtained by testing a model of *Stakeholder salience*, as the degree to which managers give priority to competing stakeholder claims, and the level of engagement, measured from qualitative and quantitative variables.

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List of acronyms

ACRONYM	MEANING
CFP	Common Fishery Policy
CS	Case Study
DST	Decision Support Tools
FITI	Fisheries Transparency Initiative
JSC	Joint Scientific Committee
MR	Management Recommendations
OT	Outcome target
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organization
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System
RBM	Result-Based Management
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
SH	Stakeholder Hub
SWA	South West Atlantic
SEA	South East Atlantic
SFPA	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems
WP	Work Package

Concepts/Definitions

Management Recommendation (MR)	In RFMS, the management recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority and operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery.
Outcome Target (OT)	Outcome targets (OTs) are specific and measurable requirements that are set by an authority to make management goals operational. An OT is a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B') or a statement of presence or absence of some entity. On the basis of relevant information, this statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time ⁵⁴ . For instance, the management objective that "the fishery should be biologically sustainable" could be expressed in terms of one or more OTs such as 'Catch < 20 000t; 'by-catch < 20%'; SSB > 30 000t; 'a catch reporting system is present', etc.

1 Introduction

The inefficiency of top-down management systems for the resolution of many problems, especially those related to fisheries management, has highlighted the need for different approaches for dealing with governance issues and interaction between government/authorities and resource user. Collaboration is the most decisive factor which would permit to achieve objectives through relationships based on mutual interdependence, compliance and interest, rather than through the control by an administrative authority.

This approach is interrelated to an effective stakeholder engagement, what many authors accepted as a principle of 'good governance', which is embedded in many national and international agendas, such as the European Union (Reed 2002; Reed et al., 2009) and the FAO Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries as a general principle.

To get a better involvement of the different stakeholders, which are interacting in multiple layers and arenas, the stakeholder analysis is becoming a relevant tool for developing innovative management approaches for fisheries management (Reed et al., 2009; Santiago et al., 2015). In fact, decision-makers have been recognizing for a long time the need to understand who is being affected by the actions, choices and decisions they are taking, and who has the power to influence their aims (Friedman & Miles, 2006).

FarFish is building on a proven track record of participatory approaches in international research and innovation projects, a participatory research, where different stakeholders are bringing their knowledge, background and resources into the design and implementation of fisheries management. Participatory processes are essential for the project to shape management actions through structured interactions, whilst also avoiding 'stakeholder fatigue'.

There are wide variety of methodologies for stakeholders' identification and prioritization discussed in the stakeholder management literature (Mitchell et al., 1997, Gago & Antolin, 2004; Parent & Deephouse, 2007, Mitchell et al., 2011). These different methodologies have given rise to widespread confusion over what is really meant by stakeholder analysis (Stoney & Winstanley, 2001). It was first considered as a valuable tool in business management, but has since progressively been adapted to different fields, including natural resource management.

Many methodologies and tools exist to manage stakeholders and various frameworks for their categorisation have been proposed. Taking into account the complexity of the FarFish project, which is inserted within its own framework i.e. the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS), the

CETMAR team⁴ has tried to review the majority approaches and have adapted them to facilitate the implementation of the RFMS. This means for example involving resource users directly into the management and decision-making processes, giving them responsibilities in order to build sense of ownership and empowerment.

Beyond different stakeholder analysis approaches, the triple circle framework of Mitchell (Mitchell et al., 1997) has become highly popular (Parent & Deephouse, 2007; Bendjenna et al., 2012). In this framework, stakeholders are categorised according to the possession of three attributes, power, legitimacy and urgency. The combination of these three attributes provides eight (8) different types of stakeholder; the most salient stakeholder possesses all three attributes, while the minor salient possess just one of them. Thus, the more attributes the stakeholder has, the greater its salience.

In others models the salience is limited to one or two attributes; Mitchell's framework is more representative of the overall profile of a stakeholder. Nevertheless, those categories are characterised by limiting thresholds, which means that each stakeholder is assigned to only one category and all stakeholders belonging to the same category are considered to have exactly the same characteristics and are treated in the same way. As a result, the classification of stakeholders into rigid categories adds an unnecessary layer of complexity to decision making about stakeholders. As these attributes are not static, an extension of the framework is needed in order to avoid that all stakeholders in a category will be considered identical, which may not be correct for two stakeholders sitting at the opposite extremes of the circle (Poplawska et al., 2015). Due to the structural and temporal limitations of the project, it is difficult to evaluate how the level of attributes of power, urgency and legitimacy vary over time, both as absolutes and as priorities.

FarFish depends heavily on the Stakeholder Hub to facilitate participatory processes within the project. Stakeholder analysis must therefore be inserted from the interaction and the creation of governance networks to obtain insights into how these networks are delivering outcomes within the project. New knowledge about stakeholders will be obtained by testing a model of Stakeholder Salience and Engagement (Beach, 2009) which combines and extends the stakeholder identification and salience theory (Mitchell, et al., 1997), ladder of stakeholder management and engagement (Friedman & Miles, 2006) and the model of stakeholder engagement and moral treatment of stakeholders (Greenwood, 2007).

It could be argued that the different approaches of transferring control are not applicable in FarFish governance networks where power and responsibility are shared among network actors (authorities and operators). Therefore, to obtain a more fine-grained view of the relationship between stakeholder salience and engagement, both quality and quantity aspects of stakeholder engagement need to be

⁴ Rosa Chapela, Marta Ballesteros, José Santiago and Duarte Vidal

examined. In addition, the construction of the urgency concept described by Mitchell, has been divided into two individual attributes: criticality and temporality, as they represent different notions. The replacement of urgency (both criticality and temporality component) thus increases the combinations of salience from eight (8) to sixteen (16) providing governance networks with an indication of how to optimise engagement with different types of stakeholders (Beach, 2009).

The different case studies will test the model of stakeholder salience and engagement, which links strategic management decisions about stakeholder salience with the quality and quantity of engagement strategies for engaging different types of stakeholders. By applying this model, the CETMAR team is responding to the question “who or what decides how stakeholders are optimally engaged by networks in delivering outcomes within FarFish?”.

2 Stakeholder analysis: selecting the framework

2.1 Defining who and what a stakeholder is

Stakeholder identification has been a common topic of analysis since Freeman's (1984) "Strategic Management: a Stakeholder Approach" seminal work, but at the present time it continues to be difficult to operationalise, despite the widespread literature on the formal mechanisms for identifying, defining and mapping stakeholders (Santiago et al., 2015). Although there are still different views on who or what exactly a stakeholder is, stakeholders have largely been defined from three different perspectives, shown in Table 1 (Reed, 2002; Friedman & Milers, 2006):

Table 1: Approaches into the stakeholder theory

Approaches	What a stakeholder is
Descriptive	<p>Broad perspective defined by groups or individuals who can actually or potentially affect or be affected by the achievement of organisational outcomes (Freeman, 1984)</p> <p>The broad approach tends to be adopted by public institutions and organisations as they have historically engaged with a broad range of social agents</p>
Instrumental	<p>Stakeholders which the organisation considers could be taken into account from the following perspectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • organisational (Freeman, 1984; Mitchell et al., 1997) • stakeholder-focal group (Friedman & Miles, 2006) • stakeholder-network (Rowley, 1997)
Normative	<p>It brings in ethical reasons as to why it should consult with stakeholders (Collins, 1989). Stakeholders who are considered to have a valid claim on the organisation e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • property rights (Donaldson & Preston, 1995) • common good (Freeman, 2004)

Many contemporary definitions of stakeholders have considered from a broad perspective, those individuals or groups who can actually or potentially affect or be affected by a decision-action or by the achievement of organizational outcomes. The descriptive approach has therefore a tendency to define stakeholders based on the perceived influence that stakeholders can have on an organisation or the range to which stakeholders are impacted by the organisational action. The narrow and instrumental perspective put the focus on how/if an institution perceives that stakeholders should be involved. The third category proposes a more narrow and normative view of stakeholders, based on the organisation's moral or contractual obligations to the stakeholders (Beach et al., 2010).

While a broad descriptive definition has the potential to bring out a large number of stakeholders to the arena, normative definitions may get the opposite impact by narrowing stakeholder groups disproportionately, which could result in important stakeholders being overlooked (Beach & Keast, 2010; Darškvienė & Bendoraitienė, 2013).

Instrumental definitions, however, strike a balance between the widest and the narrowest approaches by focusing on which stakeholders the organisation considers needed to be taken into account to achieve specific organisational outcomes. The instrumental view attempts to define the relevant groups based on their straight significance to the core interest of the organization (Mitchell et al., 1997). It is based on a pragmatic and feasible reality, taking into account clear limitations on time, resources and short-term outcomes, particularly for managers when dealing with external constraints.

The baseline for this approach is therefore stakeholders that are defined as groups or individuals who can have either an actual or potential effect on governance network outcomes (Mitchell et al., 1997), although this view bounds the stakeholder identification by restricting the stakeholder-pool to those users who can impact or may be impacted by the activities undertaken by governance networks to achieve results.

2.2 Multidimensional and instrumental approach to classify stakeholders

It is always difficult, due to timing limitations in the project agenda, to develop approaches that allow for a detailed understanding of the complexity of the social, technological, economic, environmental, political system which all stakeholders are inserted in. However, there are some approaches that can bring us closer to this path. The classification of stakeholders has been undertaken from a variety of ways in an effort to prioritise stakeholder's classification. Most of those classification systems have been using only a single dimension approach (Clarkson, 1995; Frooman & Murrell, 2005).

Other approaches to stakeholder classification take on a single instrumental perspective, focussing on cooperation by different users as a way that their support would be essential to the organization, or the degree to which stakeholders have invested different resources in the organisation. It could be said that those single approaches are too simplistic to provide a significant framework on stakeholder classification system, due to the socio-cultural components of stakeholders' networks. There exist however other stakeholder classification systems that are able to capture the multidimensional aspects of stakeholder interactions (Donaldson & Preston, 1995; Mitchell et al., 1997); such as the Mitchell's model of stakeholder identification and an alternative conceptualization of stakeholders network governance.

2.2.1 Mitchell's model of stakeholder identification

Mitchell's method presents a typology based on identification and salience concepts, an alternative structure for framing and classifying stakeholders in accordance with managerial perceptions of stakeholder characteristics (Beach et al, 2010). After a broad contribution on stakeholder definitions, these authors concluded that stakeholders are defined by the degree to which they possess three

attributes which determine the stakeholder salience: power, legitimacy, and urgency. They define 'salience' as 'the degree to which managers give priority to competing stakeholder claims' (Mitchell et al., 1997). They proposed a Venn diagram, shown in Figure 1, in which those variables will operationalize the model.

Figure 1: Stakeholder typology (adapted from Mitchell et al. 1997)

POWER: is usually unevenly distributed among actors in a relationship; it is described as the ability of an individual/group to make another individual/group do something he would not otherwise have done. The stakeholder can have power over the firm, or the firm can have power over the stakeholder. Power is therefore the extent to which a group or individual in a relationship with another has or can gain access to coercive, utilitarian, or normative means to impose its will on that other group or individual (Mitchell et al., 1997).

LEGITIMACY: the definition of legitimacy is taken from Suchman (Shuman, 1995) who defines legitimacy as 'a generalized perception or assumption that the actions of an entity are desirable, proper, or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs, and definitions'. It has been argued that legitimacy can be either normative, commitment of moral or legal obligations (Gomes & Gomes, 2007) or derivative, resulting from organisational acceptance of stakeholder claims due to their potential impact (Phillips, 2003).

URGENCY: is defined as 'the degree to which stakeholder claims call for immediate attention'. The degree depends not just on time-sensitivity, but also on how critical the relationship is with the stakeholder or the importance of their claim (Mitchell et. al, 1997). In this context, urgency implies a shifting power-balance in the relationship as a result of particular perceptions, that a stakeholder's claim is critical to the organisation and that the claim warrants immediate attention by the organisation.

A stakeholder with more attributes – power, legitimacy and urgency – will be perceived to have a higher salience. Thus, the greatest priority will be given to stakeholders who have power, legitimacy and urgency. Power and legitimacy are interrelated and the three variables can overlap.

Seven different categories result from the combinations of power, urgency and legitimacy and potential outcomes for each category. Those classes can be separated into three groups: latent, expectant and high salience (or definitive stakeholders). The key to understanding Stakeholder Salience is to grasp that the number and mix of attributes define the stakeholders salience (the priority which managers will give that group or individuals). Table 2 illustrates this – stakeholders with one attribute lack the two other attributes that would lend them enough rights, authority, voice or exercise to be highly salient and so on. Stakeholders are perceived from eight different attributes, ranging from irrelevant and requiring no action to definitive, where managers have a clear and explicit requirement to act on the stakeholder’s claims immediately:

Table 2: Stakeholder attributes depending the degree of salience

GREEN	<u>Latent stakeholders</u> : one attribute, low salience. Managers may do nothing about these stakeholders and may not even recognize them as stakeholders.
AMBER	<u>Expectant stakeholders</u> : two attributes, moderate salience. Active rather passive. Seen by managers as 'expecting something'. Likely higher-level engagement with these stakeholders.
RED	<u>Definitive stakeholders</u> : all three attributes, high salience. Managers give immediate priority to these stakeholders.

Attributes for Stakeholders salience		POWER	LEGITIMACY	URGENCY
LATENT				
<i>Low salience</i>	DORMANT		Authority	Exercise
	DISCRETIONARY	Rights		Voice
	DEMANDING	Action in favour	Access	
EXPECTANT				
<i>Moderate salience</i> <i>Active rather than passive</i>	DOMINANT			Exercise
	DANGEROUS		Authority	
	DEPENDENT	Action in favour		
DEFINITIVE				
<i>High salience</i>				
NON or POTENTIAL STAKEHOLDER		Action in favour	Authority	Exercise & Voice

i. LATENT STAKEHOLDERS

Latent stakeholders are those possessing only one of the three attributes, including (Mitchell, et al., 1997):

- **Dormant stakeholders:** stakeholders with high power but low legitimacy and low urgency. Since they have high power, they can easily impact your project objective, so you have to manage them prudently e.g. a stakeholder from top management does not take part in any meetings and has no interest in your project, but you will still watch them as they have power and you never know when they will change their mind.
- **Discretionary Stakeholders:** those are stakeholders with high legitimacy but low power and low urgency. Although these stakeholders have low power and low urgency, because of their legitimacy, you will try to fulfil their requirements. You will communicate with them regularly to provide status updates and progress; NGOs or human right organizations can be an example of discretionary stakeholders.
- **Demanding Stakeholders:** stakeholders with high urgency but low legitimacy and low power. Irritants for management, but not worth considering. These are usually very vocal and may influence other stakeholders if their requirements are not met. These stakeholders are always requiring attention. Therefore, you should manage them carefully; these include for example individuals or groups interested in the project, although they are not part in it.

ii. EXPECTANT STAKEHOLDERS

Whereas ‘one-attribute – low-salience’ stakeholders are foreseen to get a latent relationship with managers, ‘two-attribute – moderate-salience’ stakeholders are seen as ‘expecting something’, where the combination of two-attributes leads the stakeholder from a passive role to an active one. Expectant stakeholders are including three categories:

- **Dominant stakeholders:** the type of stakeholder that many theories accommodate as the only-stakeholders of an organisation or a project, as they have a high expectation of support and receive notable attention.
- **Dangerous stakeholders:** those with powerful and urgent claims but insufficient legitimacy to cause the organisation act. Conflictual relationship with the organisation in which they use different kind of power (coercive, financial or normative) to achieve objectives.
- **Dependent stakeholders:** those stakeholders who are dependent on others to carry out their will, because they lack the power to enforce their stake. Have

urgent and legitimate claims but lack power; e.g. local tenants, artisanal fishermen.

iii. DEFINITIVE STAKEHOLDERS

As ‘salience’ is defined as the degree to which individual or organizations give priority to competing stakeholder claims, it is expected that stakeholder salience will be high where all three of the stakeholder attributes (power, legitimacy and urgency) are perceived by managers to be present. Thus, the demands made by these stakeholders are rapidly responded by different organisations.

2.2.2 An alternative conceptualization of stakeholders network governance

Current Mitchell’s framework requires the description of eight categories. These categories are characterised by limiting thresholds, which means that each stakeholder would be assigned to only one category; this means that all stakeholders belonging to the same category would be considered to take exactly the same characteristics, being treated in a similar way (Poplawska et al., 2015). The classification of stakeholders into these rigid and low-flexible categories adds an unnecessary layer of difficulty on the process of stakeholder decision-making. Therefore, a more flexible approach is needed to allow all stakeholders to collectively generate an understanding of the complexity of the socio-ecological fisheries system they are working with, identifying problems and to build trust as the basis for decision making and collaborative action (Pahl-Wostl & Hare 2004). The literature tends to focus on three major and idealised governance paradigms in this respect:

- unicentric or hierarchical forms (top-down),
- multicentric (market -based)
- pluricentric (network-based) (Van Kersbergen & Van Waarden, 2004).

Currently, there is still a lack of fisheries management research integrating the knowledge from stakeholders and scientists, mostly because public fisheries policies remain viewed as top-down controlled (Mackinson et al., 2011). As opposed to the numerous consultative approaches that involve presenting a predetermined decision to stakeholders, one of the central objectives of the entire process of stakeholder engagement is to encourage decisions to emerge from the interactions of the all participants (Pade-Khene et al., 2013). Here, inclusivity becomes more relevant (in a broader sense) than representativeness, as inclusivity includes stakeholders’ access to the process itself, which is affected by how the process is conducted, how the communication-flow is driven, how decisions are weighted, and how the language-use is approached. Nevertheless, this approach implies a deep analysis of the stakeholder community which many times clashes with the temporary and normative rigidity of research projects. A key challenge for any research project and particularly for FarFish is to identify the ‘right’ stakeholders, so that management decisions fairly reflect and integrate the full diversity of the fisheries system which those stakeholders are dealing with (Lotz-Sisitka & Burt, 2006).

However, if stakeholders are not able to engage in key decisions that support and direct the project aims, such a project can end-up being irrelevant in enabling development activities.

The network governance approach is at the core of the FarFish project and it is understood to be the overarching form of a more collaborative type of governance. This network type can be distinguished as horizontally interdependent, advancing towards an operationally autonomous stakeholder, who interact through different negotiations periods, thus contributing to the production of responsible and sustainable fisheries management. Nevertheless, the literature has acknowledged that governance networks can simultaneously exhibit various hierarchical, market-based and network engagement through the adoption of a hybrid approach (Keast et al., 2006). That means governance networks are linked together with a range of stakeholders through a mixture of governance modes, functioning under hybrid arrangements and creating tensions for the network's construction. As a result, these networks face the complexity of dealing with stakeholders in relationships which operate on a relational level through reciprocity (Beach, 2010). In this sense, the stakeholder-salience model perceives the institution/organisation to be at the centre of the nexus, orchestrating stakeholder engagement processes. However, the 'centre-periphery approach' overlooks the decentred nature of stakeholder interactions (Rowley, 1997). To achieve a more acceptable and polished view of the relationship between stakeholder salience and stakeholder engagement, both quality and quantity features of stakeholder engagement should be clearly detailed (Table 3).

Table 3: Combinations of Stakeholder Salience (adapted from Beach, 2009)

COMBINATIONS OF SALIENCE	ORGANISATIONAL RESPONSE	INTEREST/ATTENTION
1. Stakeholder possesses power; claims are considered to be legitimate, critical and require immediate attention	Attends to stakeholder demands with high priority	May receive more comprehensive and immediate attention.
2. Stakeholder has power; claims are considered to be legitimate and critical but do not warrant immediate attention	Attends to stakeholder claims within in normal organisational timeframes	
3. Stakeholder has power; claims are considered to be critical and require immediate attention but are not legitimate	Manages contentious relationship in which stakeholder directly apply coercive, financial or normative power to achieve objectives	
4. Stakeholder has both power; claims are legitimate and deserve immediate attention but are not critical	Closely monitors the criticality of claims and acts if they become critical	
5. Stakeholder has no power; claims are considered to be legitimate and critical but not worthy of immediate attention	Manages stakeholder who may collaborate with other stakeholders to apply pressure to achieve objectives	Stakeholders collaborate to pressure the organisation into paying greater attention to stakeholder claims
6. Stakeholder has power and claims are considered to be critical and worthy of immediate attention but of insufficient legitimacy to cause the organisation act	Manages contentious relationship	
7. Stakeholder has power; claims are legitimate and worthy of immediate attention but not critical	Monitors stakeholder and their claims	
8. Stakeholder lack power; claims are legitimate but not critical or worthy of immediate attention	Monitors stakeholder and their claims for evidence of stakeholder coalition formation	
9. Stakeholder lacks power; claims are both critical and worthy of immediate attention but not legitimate	Monitors stakeholder	
10. Stakeholder lacks power; claims are legitimate and warrant immediate attention but are not critical	Organisation monitors stakeholder and their claims	
11. Stakeholder has both power and claims would be considered legitimate, but stakeholders are not interacting with the organisation	Organisation seeks to involve stakeholder who has no awareness of an issue or are unwilling to become involved	
12. Stakeholder has power; claims are not critical, worthy of immediate attention or legitimate	Organisation manages contentious relationship	Categories which may be paid minimal or no attention by the organisation.
13. Claims are critical but not worthy of immediate attention or legitimate and stakeholder has no power	Organisation keeps stakeholder informed	
14. Claims are legitimate, worthy of immediate attention but not critical; stakeholder hold no power	Organisation monitors stakeholder and their claims	
15. Stakeholders has no power; claims legitimate but are neither critical nor require immediate attention	Organisation keeps stakeholder informed	
16. Stakeholder has no power; claims not considered legitimate, critical or requiring immediate attention.	None	

Gaining an equilibrium between stakeholder salience and engagement is particularly pertinent for governance networks, because stakeholders could seriously disrupt networks through a withdrawal of resources, hindering the participation of their representatives, or transmitting information ‘without filters’ (profit-seeking) that can harm the actions from the rest of stakeholders.

To analyse stakeholder identification and engagement within the FarFish network, it was taking as a starting point the model of stakeholder identification and salience from Mitchel but re-building the concept of urgency into two different and individual attributes: criticality and temporality. The urgency was usually treated into the literature of stakeholder interaction as a chronological attribute (Baskerville-Morley, 2004), nevertheless, the use of urgency with both criticality and temporality features, rises the combinations of salience from eight attributes to sixteen (Beach, 2009).

3 Building the FarFish Stakeholder Hub: communication flow and stakeholder analysis

3.1 Communication flow and events

The first step in the development of the Stakeholder Hub was the design of a communication protocol, as stakeholder interaction need to be clearly structured to encourage their participation and dialogue at regional, national and European level. Considering the actions taken to underpin the communication flows to date we have structured them as follows:

- A proposal of internal communication protocol amongst WPs leaders and CS leaders was presented during the Faro WP/CS leader meeting (Nov. 2017) and approved by participants. According to this protocol, anytime WP leaders would like to contact stakeholders, they will have to do it through CS leaders with copy to CETMAR (WP1 leader) and FarFish email address –in order to ensure a continuous, follow up. Finally, CS leaders will be the ones who will contact stakeholders by CS (Figure 2). (FaFish-D1.1.)

Figure 2: Communication protocol for FarFish

FarFish needs a regular and fluent communication between all WPs in order to build a solid base for improving stakeholder interaction along the project lifetime. It is important to enhance the role of interactions with stakeholders before the different meetings are scheduled, as this is not listed properly within the communication tools, but it has a high influence in the process, being absolutely necessary for the project development. CETMAR has developed a communication strategy for these half-way interactions between stakeholders and WP leaders to minimize the number of times stakeholders are requested to collaborate (Figure 2). In addition, internal schedules for WPs dependencies regarding the project contents has been agreed with each CS leader and needs to be confirmed with stakeholders.

To understand the process followed for designing and implementing the Hub and its multiple communication tools and actions, it is important to visualize the different stages of the Hub process.

The CETMAR team have divided the process into four steps that correlate with the main events involving stakeholders and include the activities developed and to be developed. CETMAR has been so far been on stages 1-3, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Stakeholder Hub progress and stages (Red line indicates the scope, so far)

1

Before the FarFish Kick-off event

Stakeholders Template (see, Annex 1) has been submitted to CS leaders. It is a document used to build a list with key stakeholders for each CS. It is based on representativeness, relevance and availability criteria. It used the experience of the CS Leader as a *liaison person*, a proper actor who knows the reality of the fisheries in the study area. Most of the required information is personal data, contact details, type of institution or organization. It also requires an important component of subjective data (perceptions) focusing on relevant social and management issues. Once the Hub database was updated for planning the CS Kick-off event, CETMAR was in charge of guaranteeing the upgrading communication tools inventory and dynamic for stakeholder requests during the event.

2

After the FarFish CS Kick-off event & Before 1st CS event

The Stakeholder Hub database was updated, and it scheduled a tentative operators meeting by CS to support the development of MR1 proposals (first-loop) as part of the Stakeholder Hub implementation. The weeks before and after the WP & CS leader meeting in Mindelo (Cape Verde) (Nov. 2018), the CETMAR team was conducting a series of meetings with relevant operators (face-to-face and remote meetings) by CSs (Figure 1). Those meetings were scheduled from October 2018 to January 2019 in order to set the different OTs (from Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timely (SMART) features. All meetings were facilitated by CETMAR and supported by LDAC, who was acting as an intermediary (Figure 4).

Figure 4.: Interaction designed to support the development of MR1

The different CS meetings were scheduled as follows:

- Cape Verde and Seychelles CSs: A face-to-face meeting with OPAGAC (11/10/18)
- Cape Verde CS: Face-to-face meeting with ORPAGU (11/12/18)
- High Seas: South-West Atlantic-FAO 41/ South-East Atlantic-FAO 47 CSs: Remote meeting with LDAC (14/12/18)
- Senegal and Mauritania CS. Face-to-face meeting (22/01/19)

The main results from these interactions were a series of technical operator's reports elaborated both by CETMAR and LDAC ready-to-use for building Deliverable 4.3: MR1 for each CS.

3

After the MR-1 meetings

Previously to the next MR2 meeting, CETMAR has continued keeping a fluent communication with other relevant actors, especially those who develop a key role within the different CSs (Figure 5). Several meetings have been organized in order to get input for the second loop (MR2), particularly regarding the Cape Verde and the South West Atlantic CSs. It has also been important to establish a strategy with ANFACO-CECOPECA to know the priorities of the processing industry, especially in Cape Verde and Seychelles.

CETMAR has also had a meeting with IEO members, looking for synergies between the FarFish project and other scientific work developed into that high seas area. The IEO has been working in the South West Atlantic on Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) identification. Therefore, as a scientific stakeholder, we consider positive to get them on board in the development of management recommendations for this complex and sensitive area.

Figure 5: CS meetings with representatives from ANFACO-CECOPECA (left) and IEO (right)

In addition, as part of the audit process, CETMAR has scheduled a series of meetings that are framed in the activity of presenting the results from the MR1 audit by CS (Table 4). The aim of those meetings is to assess constrains and new opportunities for developing MR2, including the utility of different Decision support tools (DST). It is combined with face-to-face meetings and remote meetings, in order to facilitate the interaction. When a face-to-face meeting is scheduled regarding the project necessities it is taking into account the easiness of finding a feasible meeting point for the attendees; e.g. Las Palmas is a good meeting point for different activities as it has good flight connection.

Table 4: Working plan scheduled for the audit results presentations by CS

CS MEETINGS	Place	TYPE	DATE	TOPIC	Attendees	RELEVANCE
Senegal	Las Palmas (no-scale)	Face-to-face	15-16/Oct 19	MPR1 audit	DPM	Compulsory
					DPSP	Compulsory
					CRODT	Compulsory
					COREWAN	Compulsory
					LDAC	Compulsory
					CECAF (JSC)	Recommended
					OPROMAR	Compulsory
Mauritania	Las Palmas (no-scale)	Face-to-face	15-16/Oct 19	MPR1 audit	DARE	Compulsory
					IMROP	Compulsory
					LDAC	Compulsory
					CECAF (JSC)	Recommended
Cape Verde	Cape Verde. Mindelo	Face-to-face	21-23/ Oct 19	MPR1 audit	ORPAGU + OPAGAC	Compulsory
					ANFACO	Recommended
					INDP	Compulsory
					DNEM	Compulsory
					LDAC	Compulsory
					ICCAT	Highly recommended
Seychelles		Skype	Alternative date: 28-31/Oct 19	MPR1 audit	OPAGAC	Compulsory
					LDAC	Compulsory
					IOTC	Highly recommended
					SFA (two members)	Compulsory
High Seas	Madrid	Face-to-face	18/ Sep 19	MPR1 audit	LDAC/ARVI/IEO	Compulsory
					Argentinian operators	Highly recommended
					Taiwan operators	Highly recommended

Always taking into account the peculiarities of each CS, language barriers are being addressed with the support of technical translation services, which strengthens the stakeholder integration, improving the communication flow. This has already been done at the last 2nd annual meeting (Las Palmas) with a relevant success. Other cultural issues are being included as part of the decisions to schedule the different events and meetings; e.g. CETMAR is being aware annually of the dates of Ramadan to schedule the next meetings.

From an administrative point of view, in response to the bureaucratic difficulties of some stakeholder that require VISA, CETMAR is assisting those stakeholders in order to facilitate these procedures. It has been done many times for different events scheduled, so far.

One of the main lessons learned after working with stakeholder's participation for a long time is to avoid the well-known 'stakeholder fatigue' and make the stakeholder engagement easier and according to smooth and flexible process to guarantee their participation. In this regard, CETMAR is carrying out a strategy taking into account that sensitive issues are always respected. This is particularly important in FarFish due to the participation of African countries where the cultural and language barriers are more frequent than in most other H2020 research and innovation projects. Issues like the language, the religion and the respect of Ramadan, the participation of women, bureaucratic constraints that avoid their participation are therefore being taken into account with special care in order to facilitate the actions and activities scheduled.

When it is possible, FarFish is prioritising the involvement of women representativeness (scientists, operators and policymakers) to be selected for attending the different activities and events scheduled. FarFish is very aware of the great difficulty of addressing gender balance in the project, taking into account the cultural patterns of power that patriarchal society exercises over women. This is also affecting the internal communication within the project.

3.2 Stakeholder identification by CS leaders

FarFish is building on a proven track record of participatory approach into the international schema, integrating the principle of good governance at all stages of the policy, from the conception to the implementation in the Common Fisheries Policy (art.3). As a part of these participatory approaches, FarFish is combining two different strategies: (i) participatory research through the application of the RFMS framework, including stakeholders as project partners to bring their knowledge and resources into research design and implementation, and (ii) advance into a bottom-up methods to shape management actions based on participatory processes and structured interactions.

The main mechanism to bring together the different stakeholders (resources and competences) to the arena is the Stakeholder Hub, which is conceived in FarFish as a multi-level, a multi-stakeholder platform and a focal point for policy-makers, fishing industry, processing organizations, scientist, researcher institutions, NGOs, international organizations on fisheries management (RFMOs), and other interest groups operating within the FarFish case study areas.

The Stakeholder Hub combines physical events (e.g. workshops, conferences, CS meetings) and e-communication to match-up the project to the stakeholder agenda, where the management structure of FarFish has been constructed to match the complexity and the scale of the project. Those events are the main activities scheduled to fit the stakeholder involvement.

Stakeholder engagement describes a range of practices in which the project takes a structured approach to connecting with stakeholders (Thomson & Bebbington, 2005) and has been used for a wide variety of organisational purposes, such as to acquire organizational accountability and responsibility to stakeholders, to produce stakeholder contributions, to manage the risk, to build an organisational image or even to achieve managerial control (Owen et al., 2000). However, stakeholder engagement has been suggested as an income for strengthening the quality of outcomes by binding different ideas and perspectives, creating more robust communities through direct engagement in planning and delivery of services (Martin, 2003).

To get a better understanding of the methodology applied into the process of stakeholder identification and categorization, it is necessary to consider three main events and actions where the information has been particularly gathered from the early project stages (1st-loop) (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Stakeholder Hub main events

In this case, the CS Leaders are considered the key actors, as they have relevant knowledge in the study areas. They are also responsible for the progress, timely implementation and coordination of the work by CS; they were particularly accountable to act as an intermediary between the organizational bodies and the organisational structure of FarFish and the different stakeholders by each CS.

1 FarFish Kick-off event (June 2017)

Before and during the FarFish kick-off meeting, The CS Leaders, as *liaison persons*, were required to fill out a stakeholder template (see, Annex 1) as a starting point, containing the most relevant stakeholders by CS (FarFish-D.1.1).

Once the stakeholder list was submitted by each CS leader, it was updated in the database to schedule the 1st MR CS events. Beyond the expert opinion from the CS leaders, snow-ball sampling was utilized, thus identifying new stakeholder categories and new relevant contacts.

Figure 7 shows the number of stakeholders (institutions) identified during the first stage of this work.

Figure 7: Number of stakeholders (institutions) identified by CS⁵

It has been apparent that in the CS where there is a SFPA agreement between the EU and the coastal state that a high number of potential stakeholders has been identified/contacted, whilst in the high-seas CS the number is much lower. This is explained by the complexity, number of players and extension of the area which makes stakeholder identification more challenging in the high seas.

Taking the different definitions from stakeholder, two basic-groups of stakeholders were initially identified (Santiago et al., 2015):

1. Direct - stakeholder: those individuals and groups who use or depend on fisheries management or, ultimately are affected by it, either as beneficiaries or disadvantaged (favourable or unfavourably impacted). Authorities (policymakers), fisheries management

⁵ A complete list of different stakeholders is provided in Annex 2.

bodies (RFMOs), fishing sector, processing industry and all the local and national fishermen organizations are considered direct stakeholders (Figure 8).

2. Indirect - stakeholder: those individual or collective organizations with an interest or an intermediary role within the fisheries activity. NGOs, environmental local or national associations, recreational fishing, advisory or consultancy bodies and consumers should be considered as indirect stakeholders (Figure 8).

The balance between these two groups during this first stage was considerably in the favour of direct stakeholders, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Stakeholder identification into ‘direct or indirect’ basic groups during the 1st stage

Therefore, although this first prioritisation may marginalise certain groups, it is assumed that stakeholder categories are based on relevant interest and influence within the project.

2 FarFish MR CS Kick-off meeting (June 2018)

The Management Recommendation CS Kick-off event was the first multi-stakeholder face-to-face meeting with authorities and operators from the different CSs; it was held in Vigo (Spain) on the 26th -27th of June 2018. The meeting was titled “Strengthening fisheries sustainability outside EU”, and it was considered the first official MR kick-off meeting.

The aim of the meeting was to discuss stakeholders’ interests and needs, related to how the different stakeholders can contribute to the development of the MRs, while improving the sustainability of the fisheries by the EU distant-waters fleet. In light with interests and needs of stakeholders, potential Outcome Targets (OTs) and management recommendations were initially drafted (FarFish-D.4.2).

The CETMAR team, as organizer and host of the event, initiated a prior communication with the CS leaders to proceed with the stakeholder invitations.

Taking into account the purpose of the event, it allowed to define a new degree of discrimination between direct and indirect stakeholders, from which a new category emerged: “Non-stakeholder” (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Stakeholder identification into three main categories during the second stage:

Non-Stakeholder is considered those individuals or entities who are not properly linked to the aims of the project and their roles are not including any of the relevant attributes (power, legitimacy and urgency) to be necessarily contemplated as a potential stakeholder.

3.3 Stakeholder differentiation: an analytical categorisation

A second exercise based on an analytical categorisation (with a top-down approach) (Reed et al., 2009) was completed once the results from the FarFish MR CS Kick-off meeting (June 2018) were available. Taking the expert-knowledge from the CS leaders, it was possible to prioritise stakeholders for inclusion, making power dynamics more explicit, according to the stakeholder salience (interest and influence). The term salience means the quality of being particularly relevant, noticeable, significant or prominent, in order to know the degree to which managers give priority to competing stakeholder claims (Mitchell et al., 1997).

Here the Mitchell’s method was subsequently applied in order to get a deep-stakeholder classification based on the three main attributes: power, legitimacy and urgency. At this stage, the level of participation into the stakeholder analysis was considered from a passive consultation approach, as it would be costly if it would include interviews with every stakeholder identified in previous steps. Having the expert knowledge of the CS Leaders has allowed the project to reach a fairly good consensus on stakeholder categories.

It can be perceived now that the most important and representative group of stakeholders in FarFish corresponds to the category of ‘moderate-salience’ followed by the ‘low-salience’ and ‘high-salience’ attributes, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Stakeholder salience within FarFish regarding Mitchel method

The number of high-salience stakeholders is especially relevant. The reason is due to the requirements and limitations of the RFMS approach, which implies, among other issues, the involvement of three essential agents: the authority, the operator and the auditor.

The auditor is an independent actor with the capacity to audit the MRs performance, but here it is not taken as part of the stakeholder analysis, since the auditor is a part of the consortium, leading WP5, with certain functions and attributions assigned from the beginning of the project.

The authority is the main represented group of stakeholders according to the salience concept, with a high-salience level. The authority is a democratically accountable institution or entity entrusted with the final resource management responsibility. Therefore, there is a high-level of involvement of authorities within the FarFish project, as they are one of the most relevant stakeholder group in the development of the RFMS. Many of these authorities are taking the three attributes of power, legitimacy and urgency, although authorities with relevant power by itself does not guarantee high salience in a stakeholder-manager relationship. Power gains authority through legitimacy and it gains exercise through urgency. In addition, the participation of the different CS authorities into the events scheduled along the project lifetime, and particularly their factual implication into the definition of the OTs and the MRs by CS, are recognizable reasons for including the urgency attribute, since both power and legitimacy are already part of their institutional nature.

There is a relevant group with a moderate-salience attribute, composed of those stakeholders who 'are expecting something'. As it was commented before, a moderately salient stakeholder is identified by their possession or attributed possession of two of the three attributes. There is a high expectation from different stakeholders with the potential results and implications of FarFish in fisheries management, mainly for fishing operators. The operators play a key role in FarFish and are essential for the RFMS approach. As an organized group of resources users, they have certain legal rights in the given fisheries. They have the aim in the project to propose, support and implement MRs, which they develop based on the OTs set by the authorities. Their active role versus a passive stance into the RFMS process, suggests that the level of engagement between managers and these expectant stakeholders is likely to be higher. In addition, the operators are obligated to provide a proof of achieving these OTs through a clear supportive documentation system. They are therefore key stakeholders in terms of project dependence and interest, because the combination of two attributes leads the stakeholder to an active, with a corresponding increase in the project responsiveness to the stakeholder's interests.

It stands out that among those users with moderate-salience, the FarFish project does not currently include many stakeholders who could negatively affect the process of constitution, development and implementation of the MRs. There are few stakeholders included with urgency and power characteristics that lacks legitimacy (with the potential to be coercive or dangerous to the project). On the other hand, there is a large number of stakeholders that appear within this moderate-salience group, where the level of dependence is growing.

It is reasonable to understand that operators, especially those operating within SFPAs, maintain a high-dependency relationship with the fisheries administrations that regulate those fisheries that the operators are interested in. Their certain lack of power is therefore compatible with their urgent legitimate claims as these stakeholders depend upon others (other stakeholders or fisheries managers) for the power necessary to carry out their will. The power in this relationship is not reciprocal, its exercise is governed either through the advocacy or guardianship of other stakeholders (Mitchell et al., 1997).

Approximately a third of the stakeholders who possess a moderate-salience belong to the expectant-dominant group. This implies the appearance of an attribute linked to power and fewer urgency claims, as they may or may not ever choose to act on their claims; but with a relevant ability to act on these claims if they required. In some way, the expectations of any stakeholder perceived by managers to have power and legitimacy could be a 'matter' to managers.

The third stakeholder group with less-representation in the overall project, is characterized by the presence of a low-salience, those users with limited time, energy, and other resources to track stakeholder behaviour and to manage relationships. In this case, managers may well do nothing about these stakeholders, as they believe these stakeholders possess only one of the identifying attributes, and managers may even go so far as to not recognize those stakeholders' existence. Likewise, latent stakeholders could be likely not to give any attention or acknowledgment to the project.

If we make a more concrete analysis to evaluate the weight of each one of the categories according to the groups of direct and indirect stakeholders, there are three main categories that we should take into account, as shown in Figure 11. It should be understood that under the 'high-salience' criteria, all users are catalogued as direct stakeholders. This means that the weight of this category within the project is very high. Special mentioning should be also granted to the category 'expectant-dependent (those who have urgent legitimate claims as a dependent). They are pretty relevant for the project since a dependent stakeholder could be going through to the most salient stakeholder class, once their urgent claims have been adopted by dominant stakeholders.

Figure 11: Categories of salience by direct and indirect stakeholders

A special attention should be given to the dominant users. Depending on their positioning within the project and above all depending on whether their interests are addressed, and their expectations met. Their participation in the project will have a greater or less conflicting burden. In fact, if these users perceive a series of measures that go against their interests, they could move to the dangerous level, jeopardizing some of the project's objectives. On the other hand, it would be interesting for FarFish at least to take into account those users who possess legitimacy, but who unfortunately do not have the consideration of the managers.

It is particularly evident regarding discretionary indirect-stakeholders, that their absents of power and urgent claims, are taking no-pressure on managers to engage them into an active relationship, although managers can choose to do so. It also could be useful to communicate with them regularly to provide status updates and progress reports. In addition, those groups with demanding actions and urgent claims but having neither power nor legitimacy should ideally be taken into account.

3.4 Stakeholder engagement: re-constructing the categorisations

The initial activities scheduled to identify and make the first-categorization of the stakeholders within FarFish were established in one-way communication based on expert knowledge from CS Leaders. It contributed to a first and complete classification of the different stakeholders that were taking part in the project. The different events scheduled were also to initiate a multi-party dialogical process as part of this 'stakeholder engagement continuum'. In order to get a more accurate categorisation from the stakeholders participating in FarFish, a series of meetings with relevant operators were scheduled.

3

FarFish CS meetings to support MR1 development (Oct-Dec 2018)

The aim of these meetings was to discuss the tangible support that the operators could provide into the development of MR1. The results of these interactions provided several intermediate reports jointly conducted between CETMAR and LDAC that were used as a basis for carrying out the MRs by CS. Figure 12 shows pictures from some of these CS meetings.

Figure 12: Pictures from different CS meetings to support MR1

Beyond the initial purposes of these meetings, they were especially useful to understand the context of the interaction between different stakeholders by CS. The information provided by the operators at that stage allowed for a better understanding of some of the most relational power dynamics in each CS. Also, to perceive the diverse range of potentially differing stakeholder interests (Prell et al., 2009). Other relevant actors⁶ were also interviewed to support the categorization of those CS with a wide degree of complexity (like for example South West Atlantic CS).

At this stage, it was proposed to apply a model to connect stakeholder salience and stakeholder engagement in order to analyse the stakeholder interest. But measuring the degree of interest is difficult, so different variables are needed. Quality and quantity variables are always taking part in stakeholder engagement, so it could be tested what attributes from stakeholder salience link to quality and quantity of engagement strategies.

The model from Beach (see Table 3) was therefore taken, combining and extending the work of Mitchell et al. (1997), Friedman & Miles (2006) and Greenwood (2007). This model suggests that there may be an optimal level of engagement for the different degrees of salience assigned to the different stakeholders; where the different combinations of stakeholder salience and potential organizational responses to stakeholders (holding various combinations of power, legitimacy, criticality and temporality), are analysed together. Thus, the quantity of stakeholder engagement is considered as

⁶ An in-depth interview was conducted with an IO member to understand the power relations in the area FAO 41 and particularly in the sub-areas 41.3.1 and 41.3.2.

the number of engagement opportunities made available to stakeholders (Leach & Sabatier, 2005) from different events.

The quality of stakeholder engagement is considered as contact between governance networks and stakeholders, ranging from one-way communication to dialogical processes (Crane & Livesy, 2017). The scale for quality of engagement is derived from the ladder of stakeholder management and engagement (Friedman & Miles, 2006) which is subjectively measured through the different proactive actions and stakeholder interactions within all project activities⁷.

Following the different stakeholder models by quality and quantity, combined with the different types of salience identified (as shown in Table 3), the quality and quantity information was crossed with the type of salience that each stakeholder possess by CS. The results are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Combination of stakeholder salience and quality/quantity of engagement by SFPAs

First, we have analysed both the quality/quantity and salience by CS, initially in those CS characterized by the presence of a SFPA.

Generally, stakeholders with a low degree of salience (Stakeholder salience type=12,13,15,16 as shown in Table 3) have rarely been considered within the FarFish circle of interaction. This especially happens in the cases of Senegal, Seychelles and Cape Verde. Nevertheless, it is interesting that the

⁷ Both quality and quantity were measured under a likert scale: nothing, little, very little, normal, high and very high/ Quantity = number of interactions/Quality = type of interactions

Mauritanian CS has the presence of stakeholders with high salience rates, but with low levels of participation, both in regard to quality and quantity. Those Mauritanian stakeholders are considered relevant in terms of power and legitimacy, but some of them are not involved in the project as they do not warrant immediate attention (Stakeholder salience-type=2 in Table 3).

It is particularly noteworthy that in all four cases, there is a type of stakeholder with a high degree of salience, but it has not been taken too much into account. Normally this type of stakeholder does not fit well in a straight line within the definition of authority or operator provided by the RFMS, despite having key importance in the fisheries management. In fact, their contributions, although scarce, have always been accompanied by responses and concrete actions of great utility for the project. In this sense it is relevant to mention that some stakeholders with a moderate-level of salience are only marginally represented within the project. Those stakeholders have both power and legitimate claim, but they are still not properly interacting within the project (Stakeholder salience-type=11 as shown in Table 3). It can also be perceived how some of the stakeholders who have the attribute of power and legitimacy (authorities, mainly) have conducted unequal and unstable participation at the current point of the project. Although irreplaceable, other stakeholders with similar characteristics but who are not properly authorities, have tried to adapt their role, acting in many cases as direct intermediaries. On the other hand, there are a series of stakeholders that have a fixed and stable presence in most of the project's actions, which shows an attitude of trust and commitment. These stakeholders also have a high-moderate level of salience, so their involvement in the four CSs is very positive. This is particularly noticeable in the Senegalese CS, where besides the presence of moderate-salience (Stakeholder salience-type=5,6 in Table 3) the existence of low-salience stakeholders is accompanied by the attribute of power (Stakeholder salience-type=12).

It is important to emphasize that the level of salience and engagement is not equivalent to those stakeholders who, due to their relevance, are present in all or several CSs. The level of involvement (quantity) and the level of excellence in solving a particular issue (quality), varies depending on the CS. This is particularly striking in the case studies of the high seas, where the level of both salience and engagement varies greatly, due to the complexity of both CSs and the difficulties in the identification of key actors that are really proud and convinced to be involved in the project.

Figure 14 shows the combination of the different outgoing attributes with the level of involvement (quality and quantity) of the main stakeholders identified both in the case of the SWA and SEA (FAO areas 41 and 47).

Figure 14: Combination of stakeholder salience and quality/quantity of engagement by High seas CSs.

As it can be perceived, the South East Atlantic (FAO area 47) CS currently lacks an effective stakeholder engagement, which is explained by the fact that very little fishing activity takes place in the area. None of the stakeholders identified along the project have reached the minimum participatory levels represented by means of quality and quantity. This is especially relevant since most of the users possess a high degree of salience, between high and moderate. Even, the participation of some of the stakeholders with a high presence in all CSs. Here it becomes more tenuous. The fact of not having been able to effectively involve the management fisheries authorities (Stakeholder salience type=1,2,4) of this area has hindered the participation of other interested parties.

There are important challenges in SEA (FAO area 47) CS that must be addressed once the MR1 has been audited. A possible approach is to try to strengthen the current list of stakeholders, facilitating an active interaction within the project and perhaps incorporating new users to enrich the entire CS.

Although the South West Atlantic (FAO area 41) CS also has difficulties in involving different stakeholders, recent actions that have been taken, have generated a new scenario with high potential participation. As a general diagnosis, the level of participation of stakeholders identified within this CS has essentially low-rates. Nevertheless, it can be appreciated how the interest is growing in some of these recently incorporated stakeholders. In fact, the presence of a stakeholder who has not been actively participating in the project in previous stages is starting to be common within this CS. It is particularly newsworthy how users who have recently joined the project have managed to provide interesting reflections and contributions, generating a high-impact on the quality of the proposed content (Stakeholder salience type=7).

The potential to increase stakeholder participation within the SWA (FAO area 41) CS is high, especially if incentives for operators and authorities are clearly identified. In fact, several stakeholders identified have low rates of participation, possibly because they are neither considered sufficiently legitimate to cause and encourage the different management institutions to act, despite of claims requires immediate attention (Stakeholder salience type=6).

4 Conclusions and lessons learnt

This report has reviewed the building process of the Stakeholder Hub from the description of the communication flows and events scheduled, to the identification and analysis of the stakeholders participation. Currently, communication is fluid between the CS leaders, the CETMAR team and the rest of the project participants.

In order to avoid stakeholder fatigue, the CETMAR team and the FarFish consortium will continue following the protocol for contacting and ensuring the presence of the different stakeholders at the different events. The CETMAR team will continue to adapt its work to the stakeholder needs that may appear according to each CS, whether these needs are related to the improvement of communication and language, as bureaucratic requirements (VISA) or logistical supplies.

The CETMAR team has selected the most favourable framework that best suits the particularities of FarFish for stakeholder analysis. Thus, a framework as pragmatic as possible has been used, thinking about the temporal and structural limitations of the project.

The selection of key informants, especially the CS leaders as 'liaisons' has been an essential element for the identification of the main stakeholder by CS. However, this initial selection has been polished and adapted in relation to the objectives defined by CS. To evaluate with more precision the stakeholder's engagement, it was necessary to classify users from a theoretical point of view according to three attributes: power, legitimacy and urgency. It has provided FarFish with a well-founded base on which a classification based on quality and quantity criteria could be established later.

In general terms, the participation of different stakeholders has been increasing from the beginning of the project. The stakeholder engagement varies however substantially between CSs. There is a common issue for all CSs that participation of RFMOs could be improved. It is necessary to increase communication channels with these key-actors in forthcoming events and activities within the project.

The Seychelles and the South East Atlantic (FAO area 47) CSs are the two cases that require the greatest effort to achieve effective participation of the different users/stakeholders. Especially relevant is the low-level of involvement of several key authorities in fisheries management in the SEA CS, as well as the difficulty in identifying key operators. Here, a future involvement strategy will be to increase the number of regularly scheduled two-way dialogue into the project, particularly through the CS Leader. Regarding the Seychelles CS, it is important to note that the participation of the main operator has been high; even so, it is necessary to track the activity of other relevant operators to find the best strategy for involving them into the FarFish network. At the same time, it is necessary to increase the participation of the management authorities, so that they would acquire major responsibility in fulfilling the objectives.

In the other CSs characterized by the presence of a current SFPA i.e. Cape Verde, Senegal and Mauritania, the participation of both management authorities and operators has been very acceptable throughout the project. Perhaps, it is the Cape Verde CS who needs reinforcement in the involvement of the authorities, because much of the current weight of management responsibility has fallen to an institution that is not properly representing an authority. The involvement of operators is high in those three CSs, although it should be expanded in the second loop of the project, with the presence of new stakeholders in the arena. In the Mauritanian CS, new operators (small pelagic fishery) have been already contacted to initiate the second-loop with guaranties. A moderate number of bilateral negotiation processes to define and support the OTs followed by multi-stakeholder meetings is needed in the next steps.

Regarding the Senegalese and Cape Verde CSs, we have to highlight the presence of relevant operators in terms of power and legitimacy, but currently the national fleet and processing industry is not involved in the project. Perhaps it is not necessary that these stakeholders should be part of the network as members, but their input should be heard and taken into account. In addition, there are also a series of users with less relevance and low-salience, such as some NGOs and fishermen's organizations which do not play an important role because their objectives are outside the project, but who should be contacted and kept informed.

Special mentioning is required regarding the case of South West Atlantic (FAO area 41) CS, as it does not have an RFMO. The efforts made in this area to try to define and involve authorities and operators have been significant. Currently, relevant actors have already been contacted and identified; and they are gradually entering into the work dynamic. The participation of all these actors has been low so far, but a series of activities have already been scheduled. There is a need to continue building the network for this CS, according to the contributions that will be identified in the different activities proposed. In addition, it is needed to monitor the number of contacts between stakeholder and project network members in order to evaluate changes in salience levels.

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Annex 1. Stakeholder Template filled by CS Leaders

WP1. STAKEHOLDER INTERACTION

Table 1. All case studies (CS). Please include the main and relevant stakeholders on the CS

Case Study	Name of the CS Liaison ¹	Institution (name and type)		
Social impacts	Is there any special issue into the fishery management?			
	Yes/No. If yes, please detail the main conflict/s and main actors (key words)			
List of stakeholders relevant for your CS				
Organization name	Contact person	Contact details (phone, e-mail)	Relevant standardized data could be provided about the fishery	Comments (already involved in Management Plans, skills, leadership, etc.)

¹ The person who will be your major link in the implementation of the CS, the one that you would call on the phone and may support you in activating the other stakeholders

WP1. STAKEHOLDER INTERACTION

List of stakeholders relevant for your CS				
Organization name	Contact person	Contact details (phone, e-mail)	Relevant standardized data could be provided about the fishery	Comments (already involved in Management Plans, skills, leadership, etc.)

From the above list, circle two or three organizations that could have higher involvement in FarFish

Do you consider the above list is complete or do you think it could be completed with some other organizations you may know?

Do you need support in the identification of other relevant stakeholders? YES NO

Additional comments (expectation/interest/criticism related to FarFish)

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Annex 2. Stakeholder list

Case Study	Target Species	Stakeholder		Organisation (role)	Participation	
					Yes	No
SEYCHELLES EEZ	Yellowfin tuna; Bigeye tuna; Skipjack tuna;	Seychelles Fishing Authority	SFA	Administration	√	
		Organización Productores Asociados de Grandes Atuneros Congeladores	OPAGAC	Producer association	√	
		Asociación Nacional de Armadores de Buques Atuneros Congeladores	ANABAC/OPTUC	Producer association		x
		Indian Ocean Tuna Limited	THAI UNION	Processing company		x
		Organisation française des producteurs de thon congelé et surgelé	ORTHONGEL	Fishing company	√	
		Asociacion Nacional de Fabricantes de Conservas de pescado	ANFACO-CECOPECA	Producer Association	√	
		Fishing Boat Owners Association	FBOA	Producer association		x
		Institute for Research and Development	IRD	Research institution	√	
		Marine Conservation Society Seychelles	MCSS	NGO		x
		The Nature Conservancy	TNC	NGO		x
		Indian Ocean Federation of Artisanal Fishermen	FPAOI	Artisanal Fishermen Federation		x
		Fishing Boat Owners Association	FBOA	Artisanal Fishermen Association		x
		Artisanal Shark Fishers Association	ASFA	Artisanal Fishermen Association		x
		OCEANA	OCEANA	NGO	√	

Case Study	Target Species	Stakeholder		Organisation (role)	Participation	
					Yes	No
MAURITANIAN EEZ	Black hake; Prawn, southern; small pelagic	Resource Management and Environment Direction	DARE	Administration	√	
		Ministère des Pêches et de l'Économie Maritime	MPEM	Administration	√	
		Mauritanian Institute for Oceanographic Research and Fisheries	IMROP	Administration & research institution	√	
		Organización de Productores de Pesca Fresca del Puerto y Ría de Marín	OPROMAR	Producer association	√	
		Pelagic Freezer Association	PFA	Producer association	√	
		Garde Côtes Mauritanienne	GCM	Administration		x
		Port of Nouadhibou	PN	Administration		x
		Délégation à la surveillance des pêches et au contrôle en mer	DSPC	Administration		x
		Societe Mauritanienne De Commercialisation De Poissons	SMCP	Trader association		x
		Association pour le developpement local et l'environnement	ANNAJAH	NGO		x
		Mauritanie 2000	M2000	NGO		x
		Pêche Ecologique Génératrice de Progres Social	PECHECOPS	NGO		x
		Coopérative de pêche artisanale de Mauritanie	COPAM	Artisanal Fishermen Association		x
		Fédération libre de Pêche Artesanal	FLPA	Artisanal Fishermen Association		x
Fédération nationale de pêche de Mauritanie	FNPM	Artisanal Fishermen Federation		x		

Case Study	Target Species	Stakeholder		Organisation (role)	Participation	
					Yes	No
CAPE VERDE EEZ	Sword fish, tuna and blue shark	Direcção Nacional de Economia Marítima	DNEM	Administration	√	
		Instituto Nacional das Pescas	INDP	Administration & Research Institution	√	
		Agencia Marítima e Portuaria	AMP	Administration	√	
		Polícia Marítima/Maritime Police	PM	Administration		x
		Organización de Palangreros Guardeses	ORPAGU	Producer association	√	
		Serviços de Inspeção e Garantia de Qualidade	SIGQ	Administration		x
		Autoridade Competente para os Produtos da Pesca	ACOPESCA	Administration		x
		Operations Center for Maritime Safety	COSMAR	Administration		x
		Associação de Armadores de Pesca da Cabo Verde	APESC	Fishermen Association		x
		Overseas Fishery Cooperation Foundation	OFCF	NGO		x
		Associação de Pescadores de Mindelo	APM	Artisanal Fishermen Association		x
		Ubago Group	FRESCOMAR	Processing industry	√	

Case Study	Target Species	Stakeholder		Organisation (role)	Participation	
					Yes	No
SENEGAL EEZ	Black hake	Direction des Pêches Maritimes	DPM-MPEM	Administration	√	
		Ministère des Pêches et de l'Économie Maritime	MPEM	Administration	√	
		Direction de la Protection et de la Surveillance des Pêches	DPSP	Administration	√	
		Conservation and Research of West Africa Aquatic Mammals	COREWAN	Research institution	√	
		Oceanographic Research Centre of Dakar-Thiaroye	CRODT	Research institution	√	
		Organización de Productores de Pesca Fresca del Puerto y Ría de Marín	OPROMAR	Producer association	√	
		Senegalese Ship-owners and industrial fishing group	GAIPES	Fishing industry association		x
		National Federation of Economic Interest Groups of Fishermen	FENAGIE-PECHE	Fishermen Federation		x
		National Federation of Economic Interest Groups of Fish Traders	FENAMS	Trader Association		x
		National Collective of Artisanal Fishermen	CNPS	Artisanal Fishermen Association		x
		Association for the Promotion and Empowerment of the Actors of Maritime Artisanal Fisheries	APRAPHAM	Artisanal Fishermen Association		x

Case Study	Target Species	Stakeholder		Organisation (role)	Participation	
					Yes	No
SOUTH EAST ATLANTIC FAO47	Alfonsino; Boarfish/pelagic armourhead; orange roughy; skates, sharks, deep-sea crab; Patagonian toothfish; Wreckfish; Grenadiers nei; Blue antimora; King crab	South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation	SEAFO	Administration	√	
		Ministry of Fisheries and Marine Resources	MFMR			x
		Association of Portuguese Industrial Fishing-Boat Owners	ADAPI	Operator	√	
		Asociacion Nacional de Fabricantes de Conservas de pescado	ANFACO-CECOPESCA	Producer and processing association	√	
		Institute of Marine Research	IMR	Research institution	√	

Case Study	Target Species	Stakeholder		Organisation (role)	Participation	
					Yes	No
SOUTH WEST ATLANTIC FAO41 (Mainly subarea 41.3.1 & 41.3.2)	Argentine Hake; Australian hake; Argentine shortfin squid; Southern blue whiting	Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo Pesquero	INIDEP	Administration		√
		Cooperativa de Armadores de Pesca del Puerto de Vigo	ADAPI	Operator	√	
		Asociación Nacional de Fabricantes de Conservas de pescado	ANFACO-CECOPESCA	Producer and processing association	√	
		Chinesse Academy of Fishery Science	CAFS	Research institution	√	
		Instituto de Oceanografía	IEO	Research institution	√	
		WWF	WWF	NGO	√	

International institutions	Stakeholder		Participation	
			Yes	No
Transversal from all the different CSs	DG for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries	DGMARE	√	
	Long Distance Advisory Council	LDAC	√	
	South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation	SEAFO	√	
	European Fisheries Control Agency	EFCA	√	
	Food and Agriculture Organization	FAO	√	
	Fishery Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic (FAO)	CECAF	√	
	Joint Scientific Committee for Senegal SFPA	JSC-Senegal	√	
	Joint Scientific Committee for Mauritania SFPA	JSC-Mauritania	√	
	International Committee for the Conservation of Atlantic Tuna	ICCAT	√	
	Ministerial Conference on Fisheries Cooperation	COMHAFAT / ATLAFCO		x
	The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission	IOTC	√	
	WWF	WWF	√	